

Artificial Intelligence: With Special References to IT (Information Technology) Sector of Bangalore

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence is an integrated and multidisciplinary faces of the present scenario of the business process. It basically automates and interconnects the business processes that have implication for customers, firms, and other stakeholders. In the current competitive world the artificial intelligence has become the primary need of the business organizations, because, it has been revolutionary form of business process which is replacing the human intelligence through saving the time and cost, increasing productivity and efficiency and also the assured quality of work. The study focuses on the role of artificial intelligence in Bangalore IT sector which is called as the IT capital of India. The paper describes impact of artificial intelligence on the employees of the IT sector. The research also makes an attempt to drag out the key skills to be acquired by the IT employees in order to compete with the artificial intelligence.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, automated process, Replacing, IT sector, Impact, key skills.

Introduction

AI is an area of computer science that emphasizes the creation of intelligent machines which work and react like humans. IT sector is one of the fastest developing industries in the world by adopting AI in its work force. This technological revolution has made the companies to look for improvement and bring in more innovation and efficiency in their operations. The IT sector in India consists of two major components.

- IT services
- BPO

The sector has increased its contribution to India's GDP from 1.2% in 1998 to 7.7% in 2017. According to the industrial experts and NASSCOM (National Association of Software and Service Company), Indian IT work force will touch 30 million by 2020. Bangalore is one of the cities i.e. doing prominently well in the field of IT by adopting AI in its work force. It accounts to 25% of IT investments in India and employed more than 750000 IT professionals. So, it is called as the IT hub of India.

Review of Literature

Avneet Pannu, M. Tech Student, “ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND ITS APPLICATION IN DIFFERENT AREAS”. ISSN: 2277-3754 ISO 9001:2008 Certified International Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology (IJEIT) Volume 4, Issue 10, April 2015. The area employing the technology of artificial intelligence has seen an increase in the quality and efficiency. This paper speaks about the technology and its application areas. The study also focuses on the use of artificial intelligence in the power system stabilizes, and in the medical field, and as well as in accounting databases. The artificial intelligence gives the ability to the machines to think analytically, using concepts. Artificial intelligence has contributed tremendously to the various fields from the past two decades, and will continue to do the same. This paper has focused mainly on artificial intelligence used in the field of power system stabilizers (PSS), and it describes how the artificial intelligence techniques are used in computers games to solve the common problems, and to provide the games with more feature and as well as fun, and the researcher tells that there is bright feature in the analysis of network intrusion detection and there is also definite feature in the area of power system stabilizers (PSS).

Reshmi Banerjee, Assistant Professor, Department of Electrical Engineering, Guru Nanak Institute of Technology, Kolkata, India. “INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN ELECTRICAL, ELECTRONICS, INSTRUMENTATION AND CONTROL ENGINEERING”. Vol. 3, Issue 7, July 2015 Copyright to IJIREEICE DOI 10.17148/IJIREEICE.2015.3717, 86. Artificial intelligence is the science of automating intelligent behaviors which are achievable by humans, over the past decades the power system as grown in its size and complicity consisting of generators, transmission lines, power transformers, distribution transformers etc. The acquisition and processing of data for the use of operators and control of devices are the main building blocks of all utility control system. Though the manual calculations, technical analysis are first adopted by the power system design operation and control, as the time passed they became more complex due to the technical advancements. Today’s modern society needs continuous, and uninterrupted supply of electricity for the smooth functioning of the society, because the power system determines the growth and values of the society, so the researcher tells implementation of artificial intelligence is very important in power system.

Jochen RenzIn, Research School of Computer Science The Australian National University jochen.renz@anu.edu.au “AIBIRDS: THE ANGRY BIRDS ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE COMPETITION”. The Angry Birds AI Competition (aibirds.org) has been held in conjunction with the AI 2012, IJCAI 2013 and ECAI 2014 conferences and will be held again at the IJCAI 2015 conference. In this paper of AIBIRDS, Jochen RenzIn describes the difficulties and challenges of artificial intelligence and why it is important bring in artificial intelligence that react with the real world, and the research emphasizes on past competition and describes which method were successful. The basic angry bird artificial intelligence game was developed with the intent of teaching kids about artificial intelligence and programming in a playful way which helps them to become more creative and skilful. They are planning to conduct a competition for Scholl children based on AIBIRDS snap implementation. At the upcoming competition at IJCAI 2015, they plan to have a new competitive track where two agents try to solve game levels with alternating shots. At the beginning the two agents each submit a concealed offer as to how many points they are willing to pay for the right of the first shot. The agent with the higher offer starts and the agent with the winning shot get all the points of the level. If the agent with the higher offer wins the level, the offered points are paid to the other agent. This competitive variant is easily possible with a small modification to the client/server communication protocol. The aim is to encourage agents to analyze game levels and to evaluate actions in advance rather than winning by a lucky shot. In addition it could make the competition interesting for game theory researchers.

Statement of Problem

An investigation found that the revolution in the field of AI may replace humans, machines may takeover human jobs, and also the study tells that by 2020, 85% of the customers relationships will be done by AI. Like attending calls, mailing, etc. which is a worried factor among the clients

Objectives

- Role of Artificial Intelligence in IT hub.
- Impact of AI on employees of IT sector.
- The key skills need to be adopted by the IT employees to compete with the standard of AI.

Methodology

In this paper, for the first objective the secondary data has been used to find the relevant information and facts. For the second and third objectives primary data has been used, which were collected through the questionnaire method among the sample group of IT employees in Bangalore.

The basic statistical tools were used wherever required. Deferent charts were used for interpretation.

Interpretation

Among the IT professionals who responded to this survey 60% are men and 40% are women.

The majority of the people who responded to this survey belong to the age group between 36-45 years.

Among the 100 respondents 51% of them agree that AI is more effective than human intelligence.

Among the total respondents 55% of them have expressed negative opinion about the complete replacement of AI over Human intelligence.

Among the 100 IT employees taken to survey, 27% of people have the fear of losing their job due to AI.

To what extent does the AI is helping in your daily tasks? (grade it accordingly)

The survey tells that 40 to 60% AI is helping them in their daily tasks.

Among the total respondents 38% of the IT employees say that time and cost effectiveness leads the companies to go for AI and next stands the more productivity at 34%.

Among the total respondents, 51% of them say yes to the adaptation of AI, as it brings in more accuracy, effectiveness and efficiency and saves money and cost. Whereas 49% of the respondents say no, the main reasons they give are,

- It causes unemployment,
- AI requires Human intelligence to handle.

Among the total respondents 45% of them say that to the extent of 41-60% AI is being adopted in their respective companies.

Among the total number of respondents only 40% of employees are able to cop-up with the AI.

The employees are not able to cop-up with the AI because,

- Lack of training and Educational qualification
- Lack of knowledge of advance technology.

Among the respondents, 71% employees say that they should have the ability to adopt to the new technologies, and 56% say that proper training helps them adopt to the AI.

Findings

- The above survey shows that AI is more effective than human intelligence
- The employees are positive towards the adoption of AI
- AI cannot fully overtake the human intelligence
- Only 40% of people are able to cop-up with the AI
- 35% are not able to do so because: they lack proper educational qualification, training and knowledge about advance technology. This is where the employees need to improve their skills in order to develop positive attitude towards the AI.

Conclusion

In the current scenario AI has become the major priority of the organization. As per the study it has been evident that the major part of the companies has been acquired by the AI. So the human intelligence has become limited even though the AI is developed on human intelligence. The employees of IT sector are still struggling to cop-up with the standards of AI. So this struggling situation can be solved by giving proper training to the employees, hiring the employees who have proper educational qualification and who can understand the situation better and change accordingly, and the employees should be open to adopt the new changes in technology.

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